

Derivation of a plastic strain limit for the finite element analysis of DHY and fillet welds in normal strength steel connections

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ABSTRACT

Complex structural steel connections are nowadays increasingly modelled and calculated with the finite element method. For the modelling of the joint components, two important parts are required. First, the geometry must be captured in a realistic and safe way. Second, a material model described by a material characteristic curve and a plastic strain limit must be inserted. For plates and bolts, the new prEN 1993-1-14 offers some rules concerning the material model. Therein, the plastic strain limit for plates of normal strength steel is set to 5%. Unfortunately, there are no regulations on the material behaviour for welds provided. Since there is no alternative information given, the 5%-limit often is adopted for the maximum permitted plastic strain in the weld elements. This assumption should be questioned critically. In contrast to a plate with a uniform cross section, there is a distinctive notch effect due to the weld geometry, which leads to a complex stress state in the weld area. Furthermore, there is the influence of residual stresses resulting from the rapid heating and cooling during the welding process. To analyse the stress-strain behaviour of a welded joint in more detail, tensile tests were carried out on welded cross-joint specimens with DHY and fillet welds in the research laboratory of the Institute for Steel Construction and Materials Mechanics at the Technical University of Darmstadt. The deformations during the testing were measured by the digital image correlation method. Based on the experimental results and some practical assumptions, a plastic strain limit for welds can be derived.

Keywords: plastic strain limit, welds, finite element analysis, material behaviour

INTRODUCTION

In the current practice of structural design, the finite element analysis becomes increasingly important for nearly all fields of engineering work. The design of complex buildings, the advancing digitalisation process and the pursuit of economic efficiency are responsible for this shift from the classic structural design into a digital design method. Concerning steel constructions, not only the structural analysis of the global system, but also the connections are nowadays modelled, calculated and verified with the help of the finite element analysis. Besides bolts, welds are one of the mostly used joint components. Therefore, it is very important to have a simple and user-friendly weld model, which provides safe and economic results in terms of optimized weld thicknesses. The finite element modelling of a welded connection can be divided into two major tasks. First, the weld geometry must be modelled and divided into a sufficient mesh of elements. Second, the material behaviour of the weld respectively the specific stress-strain-curve must be applied to the weld elements. To enable stress redistribution within the weld model, which is required for an economic joint design, the ductility and plastic reserves of the weld must be considered. Therefore, a maximum plastic strain as a resistance criterion has to be defined for the finite element analysis.

1 STATE OF STANDARDISATION AND RESEARCH

1.1 State of standardisation

EN 1993-1-8 (1)

The European design standard for connections, the EN 1993-1-8, provides two verification procedures for welds: the directional verification method considering the individual stress components and the simplified procedure, which assumes all acting forces as shear stresses. The resistance side of both verification methods is based on component tests, which makes the design methods of the EN 1993-1-8 a nominal stress concept. They do not provide any information about the local material behaviour in the weld and thus is not suitable for the finite element analysis.

prEN 1993-1-14 (2)

For plates and bolts, the new prEN 1993-1-14 offers some rules concerning the material model. In (2) chapter 8.1.5 for the structural resistance R_{comp} there are two criteria given (fig. 1). Criterion 1 regulates the maximum permitted load and criterion 2 the maximum permitted plastic strain in the component. For plates, the maximum permitted plastic strain is set to 5%. For bolts, 25% of the elongation at failure shall be assumed (prEN 1993-1-14 8.1.5 (2)). For welds there is no resistance criterion provided. This is why, this paper deals with the derivation of a plastic strain limit for welds in the finite element analysis.

Fig. 1. Determination of structural resistance by material non-linear analysis ((2) fig. 8.1)

FKM guideline (3)

For the static weld verification by means of finite element analysis, the FKM guideline (3) provides two design approaches (fig. 2): the notch concept with the resistance $\sigma_{sk,w}$ (eq. (1)) and the structural concept with the resistance $\sigma_{kk,w}$ (eq. (2)). In both concepts, the resistance stress is increased by a plastic ratio n_{pl} . In the formula of n_{pl} (eq. (3)), the plastic shape number K_p considers the plastic load reserve (fully plastic load capacity/elastic limit load) in the weld. In addition, the plastic strain limit $\epsilon_{tr} = 5\%$, and the yield strength $R_p = 355 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (for S355) are included in the formula of n_{pl} .

Fig. 2. Notch and structural stress concept (4)

Notch stress resistance:

$$\sigma_{sk,w} = R_p \cdot \alpha_w \cdot n_{pl} \quad (1)$$

Structural stress resistance:

$$\sigma_{kk,w} = R_p \cdot n_{pl} \quad (2)$$

Plastic ration:

$$n_{pl} = \min \left(\sqrt{\frac{E \cdot \epsilon_{ertr}}{R_p}}; K_p \right) \quad (3)$$

However, the consideration of a plastic ratio for welded components in the notch or structural concept is only permitted for through-welded connections or welds that cover the cross-section ((3) chapter 3.3.2.1). Furthermore, the FKM guideline has not been introduced by the building authorities and therefore can only be applied in Germany in approvals.

1.2 State of research

Current research offers a wide range of experimental and numerical investigations on the material behaviour of welds. For example, in the dissertation of Hölbling (5), the influence of the welding process on the load-bearing capacity of welds for normal strength steels is investigated by means of finite element analysis. Investigations concerning the material behaviour of fillet welds on high-strength steels are documented in detail by Rasche (6) and Stroetmann (7).

Hildebrand (8), Loose (9) and Radaj (10) studied the influences of temperature and residual stresses on the weld material properties by simulating the welding process with the finite element method.

Investigations on the influence of the weld geometry and the load direction on the static load-bearing capacity can be found in the reports of Deng (11), Callele (12) and Miazga (13). In addition, there are some useful hints given in the papers of Lippard (14), Dong (15) and Xiao (16) concerning the effect of the weld geometry in a finite element analysis. Although they mainly deal with fatigue problems, they nevertheless can be transferred in certain parts to a static analysis.

1.3 State of software development

RFEM (Dlubal)

In the latest version of the finite element software RFEM6 from Dlubal (version 6.05.0003) there is the opportunity to model the plastic behaviour of welded connections. In how far the applied model parameters and resistance criteria are reliable or economical is part of current investigations.

IDEA StatiCa

The software IDEA StatiCa from SCIA Software GmbH works with the Component Based Finite Element Method (CBFEM) (17). The welds are represented in the model as shell-equivalent elements. The weld stresses σ_{\perp} , τ_{\perp} and τ_{\parallel} are calculated from the stresses in the connected plates. The assigned material law of the weld element is elastic-plastic, analogous to the steel sheet, whereby the plastic strain limit is set to 5% (17). This approach must be critically questioned.

2 TENSILE TESTS WITH DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

2.1 Experimental Program and test setup

In the research laboratory of the Institute for Steel Construction and Materials Mechanics at the Technical University of Darmstadt tensile tests were carried out in four test series with four different weld geometries (see fig. 3a). The specimens were manufactured by the steel construction company Donges SteelTec in Darmstadt with the MAG welding process. In the first step three plates with a thickness of 35 mm (weld thickness 7 mm) or 50 mm (weld thickness 10 mm) were welded to form a cross-joint. Afterwards the welded piece was cut into 25 mm thick slices (fig. 3b). By this, approximately the same weld properties were achieved in all specimens.

Fig. 3. a) Test series with four weld geometries b) Specimens with similar weld properties

For the tensile tests, the specimens were installed in a 1000 kN testing machine (fig. 4). During the testing an optical measurement system was used to capture the deformation on the surface of the specimens. In the paper “Investigations on the material behaviour of weld seams for the use in finite element analyses” (18) the test setup and the optical measurement system are described in detail.

Fig. 4. Test setup: 1000 kN testing machine and optical measurement system

2.2 Experimental results – strain images and fracture zone

With the software VIC3d, based on the digital image correlation method (19), the strains in the weld area can be determined in x, y and xy-direction. However, for a reliable analysis the different strain components must be recalculated into the principal strains ε_1 and ε_2 (fig. 5 and eq. (4), (5)).

1st and 2nd principal strain:

$$\varepsilon_{1,2} = \frac{\varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y}{2} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\gamma_{xy}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Angle of the 2nd principal strain:

$$\tan 2\varphi^* = \frac{\gamma_{xy}}{\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 5. Principal strains ε_1 and ε_2

In table 1, the DIC-images of the principal strains ε_1 and ε_2 due to the tensile loading on a specimen with a DHY-weld and on a specimen with a fillet weld, each with 7 mm weld thickness, are shown. The images correspond to the time just before the first crack appears in the weld area. The strain-scale of ε_1 (0 – 12%), and ε_2 (-10% – 0) are each the same, so the results are well comparable.

Table 1: Principal strains and fracture surfaces for a DHY and a fillet weld

Weld type	ε_1	ε_2	Fracture surface + ε_1
DHY-Weld 7mm			
Fillet-Weld 7 mm			

In addition to the strain images, the fracture surface overlaid with the 1st principal strain is shown in table 1. Further information on the strain results and the derivation of the fracture zone are provided by Kuntsche (18). The fracture zone runs within the weld metal. The angle of the fracture zone to the horizontal plate corresponds to the angle of the main shear strain in the weld area (eq. (6)).

$$\text{Angle of the main shear strain:} \quad \varphi^{**} = 45 + \varphi^* \quad (6)$$

This relation is not surprising, as the fracture surface also has some similarities to a shear crack. There are currently further investigations on the fracture surface and the associated failure mode running.

3 DERIVATION OF A PLASTIC STRAIN LIMIT

3.1 Basic strain value for the plastic strain limit

The strain distribution of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 in table 1 show the complex strain state in the weld due to the weld geometry. In contrast to a plate with a uniform cross section there is not only a 1st principal strain but also a distinctive 2nd principal strain which cannot be neglected. For a complex stress state, there exist strength or failure hypotheses, which capture the 1st and 2nd principal stresses and provide one decisive equivalent stress (e.g. von Mises, Tresca). For the elastic material behaviour the stresses can easily be recalculated into the strains ($\epsilon = \sigma / E$). However, after reaching the yield strength the material behaves non-linear and a linear transfer of the equivalent stress to an equivalent strain is not permitted any longer. For this reason, each principal strain direction must be dealt with separately, whereby one principal strain has to be chosen as the basic value.

The 1st principal strain ϵ_1 is defined as the basic value for the plastic strain limit.

A possible consideration of the 2nd principal strain is described in chapter 3.4. Another important effect on the plastic strain limit has the welding process itself. During the rapid heating and cooling of the material, residual stresses arise in the weld area. In chapter 3.5 there are some ideas given, how to determine these residual stresses in detail and evaluate their influence on the plastic strain limit.

3.2 Definition of a reference point

Due to the complex stress state, there is a very inhomogeneous strain distribution in the weld area. If a plastic strain limit shall be applied to a finite element analysis, a reference point has to be defined. As the plastic strain limit is a resistance criterion for the weld, the reference point has to be placed along the fracture zone (see chapter 2.2). The length of the fracture zone of the DHY-weld with 7 mm weld thickness is $a_f = 12$ mm (fig. 6a). In fact, there are very high strains close to the weld root. This is due to the notch effect in this area, which leads to a significant stress concentration. Unfortunately, the strains in the area very close to the weld root (0 – 2 mm) cannot be captured at the time of the crack initiation, as the primer already started to peel off. The strain values ϵ_1 along the other points of the fracture zone at crack initiation are shown in figure 6b. From the weld root to the weld surface, the strains ϵ_1 decrease exponential until 30% of the fracture length $a_f = 12$ mm (12 mm * $0.3 = 3.6$ mm). Afterwards the curve is approximately linear.

Fig. 6. a) DIC-strain image ϵ_1 at crack initiation b) Strain - distance - curve along the fracture zone

The plastic strain is a resistance criterion for a static analysis. There are no fatigue calculations or crack simulations required, so the area of the weld root with its high notch stresses can be neglected.

The reference point P_0 is defined along the fracture zone at $0.3 \cdot a_f$ from the weld root (fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Definition of the reference point P_0

The reference point P_0 must be explicitly modelled within the finite element model of the weld to determine the 1st principal strain ϵ_{1,P_0} in this point and compare it to the plastic strain limit.

3.3 The resistance criterion for the weld

In the case of welded connections, it is very difficult to define a useful elongation at failure due to the complex stress state in the weld area, particularly after crack initiation. The decisive plastic strain limit for the static finite element analysis of welds should therefore be assumed as a criterion before the first crack. With the measured data of the DIC (strain-images and corresponding load) the load-strain behaviour in any point of the welded connection can be plotted in a specific material curve. For the determination of the start of cracking, the load-strain-curve of a point P_G in the unaffected base material and the reference point P_0 in the weld metal are drawn in figure 8.

Fig. 8. Load-strain behaviour in the base material (P_G) and in the reference Point (P_0)

At the beginning of the tensile test, both material curves are linear. At a load level of 120 kN the weld material (P_0) begins to plasticize. There is no distinctive yield strength but rather a smooth transition to a non-linear material behaviour. At 295 kN the base material (P_G) reaches its yield strength and begins to plasticize. In contrast to the weld material curve (P_0) there is a clear yield plateau in the base material curve (P_G). The transition from the linear elastic to the non-linear plastic behaviour of the base material is also marked by a slight load drop in the material curve of the weld (P_0).

At a load level of 350 kN a sudden and significant load drop can be recognized in the curve of the base material (P_G). The test load decreases rapidly, which is a clear indication for a crack in the specimen. However, the associated strains in the point P_G stay nearly the same. The crack thus cannot be in the base material but rather marks the start of cracking in the weld. After the crack initiation, the load slowly decreases with increasing strains in the weld material (P_0) until the final fracture.

The plastic strain at crack initiation in the weld is defined as the resistance criterion.

This assumption has some important and very practical reasons:

- The DIC-measurement is very difficult after the crack initiation since the primer for the speckle pattern peels off. The first crack however can be determined very precisely.
- Concerning the finite element analysis, the modelling of a weld is quite simple, until it starts to crack. To simulate a crack initiation and the subsequent crack growth in a finite element model until a final failure, a very profound knowledge of fracture mechanics is required.
- In the practical use under static loads a crack in a welded connection always should be prevented as it provides many problems concerning corrosion and fatigue damage.

3.4 Consideration of the multi-axial strain state in the weld

The 1st principal strain ϵ_1 in the welded specimen is significantly lower than an equivalent principal strain in a uni-axial tensile test with a constant cross section. This is due to the geometry of the weld and its eccentricity to the load axis, which leads to a complex strain state in the weld area. To evaluate the influence of the weld eccentricity, four grades of eccentricity are introduced in table 2.

Table 2: Weld geometries and their grade of eccentricity

Weld type	DY-weld	DHY-weld	DHY+ fillet weld	Fillet weld
Geometry and eccentricity				
Grade of eccentricity	0	1	2	3

For a DY-weld or fully welded connection without any eccentricity the grade of eccentricity is “0”. There is no gap between the welds and the load can flow unimpeded into the connected plate. For all the other weld types in table 2 the load must be redirected around the gap and notch stresses arise. Depending on the eccentricity of the weld axes the notch effect can be rated from “1” for DHY-welds with a low influence to “3” for a fillet weld with a very high influence.

For the consideration of a multi-axial strain state, the reduction factor k_E is introduced (eq. (7)).

$$\epsilon_{1,\text{multi-axial}} = \epsilon_{1,\text{uni-axial}} \cdot k_E \quad (7)$$

The reduction factor k_E depends on the grade of eccentricity (see table 2). For the determination of k_E numerical and experimental investigations are currently running at the Institute for Steel Construction and Materials Mechanics at the Technical University of Darmstadt.

3.5 Influence of residual stresses

In addition to the complex strain state due to the weld geometry there are residual stresses from the welding process, which lead to plastic deformation in the weld area and thus reduce the plastic strain limit. The residual stresses can be divided into a longitudinal and transverse component (fig. 9a + b).

Fig. 9. a) Longitudinal residual stresses b) Transverse residual stresses ((10))

By the sawing process of the specimens the longitudinal residual stresses change into internal compressive stresses in the weld (8). These compressive stresses act opposite to the stresses in the weld from the external tensile load. The DIC-results thus are on the unsafe side, as in a continuous weld the longitudinal stresses act as tensile stresses and have to be superposed with an external tensile load. The transverse residual stresses in the specimens are not effected by the sawing process.

For the consideration of the residual stresses two reduction factors are introduced (eq. (8)).

$$\varepsilon_{1,RS} = \varepsilon_1 \cdot (k_{RS,L} + k_{RS,T}) \quad (8)$$

The reduction factors $k_{RS,L}$ and $k_{RS,T}$ are determined by means of a numeric welding simulation. The results are validated by a comparison between the tensile test on the four test series, including the residual stresses and tensile tests on specimens of the same test series, where the residual stresses are decreased to a minimum by a stress-relieved heat treatment.

3.6 Proposal for a plastic strain limit formula

In the previous chapters, the different influencing factors on the plastic strain limit for welds were explained. All the factors can be summarized in the following formula (eq. (9)):

$$\varepsilon_{1,P0} \leq \varepsilon_{1,pl,c} * k_E * (k_{RS,L} + k_{RS,T}) \quad (9)$$

$\varepsilon_{1,P0}$: The 1st principal strain in the reference point P_0 (out of the finite element analysis)

$\varepsilon_{1,pl,c}$: The basic value for the plastic strain limit defined as the 1st principal strain in the weld under an uni-axial loading at the time of crack initiation

k_E : The reduction factor for the multi-axial strain state in the weld

$k_{RS,L}$: The reduction factor for the longitudinal residual stresses

$k_{RS,T}$: The reduction factor for the transverse residual stresses

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

For the verification of welded connections by means of finite element analysis, there currently still is a lack of a weld-specific material model in practice. Especially the plastic strain limit, which is required for an economic weld design, is not regulated yet. In this paper a formula for a plastic strain limit as a resistance criterion for the finite element analysis of welds is proposed. For the analysis of the decisive strains in the weld a reference point is defined. As a basic value for the plastic strain limit the 1st principal strain in the weld at the first crack initiation is assumed. The proposal of the plastic strain limit formula considers the complex strain state in the weld area due to the weld geometry as well as the residual stresses from the welding process. The determination of the different influencing factors are part of current research at the Institute for Steel Construction and Materials Mechanics.

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